

**USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR MARKETING
(A CASE STUDY OF JW MARRIOTT, CHANDIGARH)**

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“The management process that identifies, anticipates and supplies customer requirements efficiently and profitably”

Abstract

Social media present a golden opportunity for the hospitality industry to make greater contact with its customers, with an ultimate goal of developing a partnership for brand growth and development. Underlying that opportunity is the twin dangers that hospitality operators will mishandle their social media connections or that customer (and the media themselves) will move on, leaving the industry behind. So, just as hotels and some restaurants have built their websites, they now have to make sure that their site is optimized for search engines, have mobile apps, and, more to the point, keep customers involved in a conversation about the operation. Although many hotel chains have embraced mobile apps, Facebook, and other channels, others are hardly represented at all in the social media firmament. In this paper an attempt is made to study the most effective social media for Marketing of goods and service, the impact of social media on the customer and to know the satisfaction level of the customer regarding the services of the JW Marriott hotel, Chandigarh.

KEY WORDS: Social media, Marketing of goods and services, Satisfaction level of customers.

INTRODUCTION

Marketing acts a support system to the sales team by propagating the message and information to the target audience. Marketing techniques include choosing target markets through market analysis and market segmentation, as well as understanding consumer behavior and advertising a product's value to the customer.

“The all-embracing function that links the business with customer needs and wants in order to get the right product to the right place at the right time”.

JW MARRIOTT CHANDIGARH

Marriott International opens its first JW Marriott Hotel in North India

CHANDIGARH, INDIA- June 29, 2011- Having created landmark of its JW Marriott brand at Juhu in Mumbai, the business capital of India, Marriott international Inc., a global lodging leader, today repeats this extraordinary achievement in the city of Chandigarh with the launch of its JW Marriott Chandigarh- the first JW Marriott hotel in North India and the second in the country.

This hotel that spells understand luxury, offer 165 spacious rooms including 4 suites and 1 presidential suit elegantly designed in a unique opened layout. The Grand Ballroom has a majestic

ceiling height of over 6 meters, adorned with crystal chandeliers. The available area of 16500 sq. feet includes indoor and outdoor space for meeting and banqueting facility making it an ideal choice to host elegant weddings, social events, meeting and conferences. Other facilities include Business center, a full service executive lounge and the award winning Quan Spa, an oasis of relaxation and rejuvenation.

So whether travelling to Chandigarh on business or leisure, JW Marriott Chandigarh is your luxury designation.

The Café@JW

The Café@JW is a contemporary all day dining restaurant that serves an assortment of authentic international cuisine which include Asian Salads, Cantonese, Sushi, Thai and Vietnamese, Malay Chinese Barbecue, Dim Sum and Dumplings, Chilled Seafood, Condiments and dressings, Indian Tandoori and Curries crafted by expert Indian and expat Chefs. The café offers an extensive buffet spread and a la carte specialties for breakfast, lunch and dinner.

Chandigarh Baking Company

Fondly known as CBC, the bakery welcome you with a wonderful aroma of brewed coffees and freshly baked goodies. Indulge your taste buds and dig into some sinful cakes and pastries, made-to-order sandwiches and burgers, and a variety of hand-made breads and chocolates.

The Lounge

The lounge is the heart and the soul of the hotel where guests feel welcome and free to be themselves. The ambience is intimate yet lively, elegantly designed and is conducive to social or business meeting. The lounge is transitional in nature and changes its mood, setting and menu as the day goes on.

Saffron

The Indian fine dining restaurant Saffron is an ode to the flavors of the North West frontier region. The restaurant bring out the richness of the food from the pre-partition Punjab; intact with its rustic simplicity and authenticity

Oregano Restaurant and Bar

Oregano restaurant and bar, with its trattoria charm exudes warmth and homeliness. This authentic, fine dining Italian restaurant and bar offers an exotic mix of traditional style cooking infused with fresh herbs and spice which are unique to the cuisine

The Executive Lounge

This is our private lounge, an indulgent luxury available to guests who want that extra special care. It is offered as a complimentary benefit to our most loyal guests. The Executive Lounge provides complimentary breakfast, high tea and a happy hour service.

Banquets and Meeting Rooms

The state-of-the-art banqueting facilities in the hotel are spread over an area of 16500 sq.ft., indoors and outdoors. The Grand Ballroom with a majestic ceiling height of 6 meters and with 6295 sq.ft. is further divisible into 4 break-away hall; Ballroom 1-1722 sq.; Ballroom 2-2421 sq.ft.; Ballroom 3-2152 sq. fit accommodating a maximum of 900 person in total.

The Living Room

Based around the concept of NEW YORK style apartment, The Living room is a space for business meeting with a difference. With an open kitchen, a lounging area and an open foyer, it offers a casual and relaxed environment for business meetings and blends the comforts of a living area with the benefits of tech-savvy meeting rooms.

Business Centre

Our state-of-the-art business Centre provides Windows and Mac personal computers. Other facilities include a meeting room with a seating capacity varying from 8 to 10 persons. The Boardroom is equipped with an overhead projector, clip boards, 42 inch LCD, Conference Call Butler, laser pointers and laptops on request.

Accommodations

With 164 spacious luxury rooms, set in a unique open layout, the JW Marriott Chandigarh offers aristocratic elegance and absolute comfort. The hotel has 128 deluxe rooms, 35 executive rooms, 4 suites and 1 Presidential suite.

A wide range of amenities and service are available in all rooms which include;

- 42 inch LCD
- Multimedia Panels
- High-speed wireless internet connectivity
- DVD player
- I-Home docking station
- Private LDD telephone and fax number
- Bathroom Amenities
- In-room safe
- Mini-bar
- Coffee
- Valet service

- Doctor on call

In Room Dining

At the JW Marriott Chandigarh, In Room Dining is our way of creating a restaurant quality dining experience in the privacy and comfort of a guest room.

At Your Service

At Your Service is a one-stop shop taking care of all guest needs including EP ABX functions, in-room dining, Housekeeping and other requests.

Airport Services

Airport Services provide airport assistance during arrival and departure of guests.

Laundry Services

Available 24 hours seven day a week, the services include Laundry, Dry Cleaning and pressing. Laundry and Dry Cleaning items picked up before 11:00 am will be returned the same day after 6:00 pm.

Quan Spa

The JW Marriott brings award winning Quan Spa to the city beautiful. Quan is the Chinese word for ‘the source of pure water’ and here we offer our guests an oasis of healing and rejuvenation.

Recreational Service

The hotel offers multiple recreation options that are meant to help you gear up, relax or unwind, at the start or end of day.

USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR MARKETING

Social media has a impact on the practice of customer experience management in a huge way since communication media have developed into a number of different forms including text, image, audio, and video through the development of forums, message boards, photo sharing, search engine marketing video sharing, social network, professional networks and micro-blogging sites. Customer have now started their own communication, share collaborate information and experience about product and service. The traditional method of customer feedback is not preferred anyone, the peer to peer recommendation and review through social network is more acceptable. It is because of such media outlets that the public have become important players in coverage of crisis.

As *Bill gates* once said that for a corporation, the “unhappy customers are its greatest source of learning” and these words are often used in business meeting and training workshop. A company could get important information from their customer whether they are happy or not with

the product or service so that the information can help them improve and have a better standing in the market.

Social media has proven to be a game changer in the way of communication between people. As now the customer post their experience on social networking sites which goes viral thus it could have a positive and negative both on the company.

These day companies are trying their best to attract customers through social by holding contest, telling them what's new with their product or service, discount, package etc. so that the interaction stays high and people are aware about the on-going activities. As the interaction increases the companies get a better idea about what their customer prefer and they try to deliver according to their needs.

JW Marriott Chandigarh takes social media as an integral part of their activities to connect with their customer. Various activities used by the organization to connect with their customer and keep them engaged with the activities happening in the hotel.

JW Marriott uses Facebook, Pinterest, Google+ and Instagram to reach out to their customers.

OBJECTIVE OF THESTUDY

Considering the importance of social media of marketing, the main objectives of my study in relation to J W Marriott, Chandigarh are delineated below as:

- To understand the most effective social media for Marketing of goods and service.
- To examine the impact of social media on the customer.
- To study the perception of brand by its consumer based on its social media.
- To understand what attract the customers on social media.
- To know the satisfaction level of the customer regarding the services of the hotel.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is exploratory and descriptive in nature. Data was collected both from primary and secondary sources. Secondary data was collected from annual reports of JW Marriott, newspapers and internet etc. Primary data through face-to-face conversation from employees and through questionnaire being filled by the bank customers with sample size 153 in the year 2015. Convenience sample was done for the questionnaire to be filled within the JW Marriott Chandigarh Hotel as it was affected by the time available to the customer. The statistical tools used are: Graphical representation, Tabular representation, Excel sheet.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Q1. Do you follow JW Marriott Chandigarh on any social media sites?

Technology has become an important part of our lives. From the above graph it can be seen that out of 153 people 142 people follow JW Marriott Chandigarh on social networking sites. Thus it helps us to know that the use social media for the organization is important as large number of people depend on social media.

Q2. Which site do you follow JW Marriott Chandigarh most on

Out of 153 people 111 follow JW Marriott Chandigarh on Facebook, 32 follow on twitter, 8 follow on pinterest and 2 follow on instagram as shown in the above graph.

Q3. Is social media better than traditional media in the area of customer experience management?

In the fast moving world people don't have time for read letters (traditional media). With the growing popularity of internet most of the people are now dependent on social media. Out of 153 people 149 people think that social media is better than traditional media.

Q4. Rank in order of preference from where do you get the maximum information about JW Marriott Chandigarh?

Direct Mail

Facebook

Twitter

Pinterest

Instagram

This is clear from the table that people get maximum information about JW Marriott Chandigarh facebook and Twitter. Where at the least mode of information is direct mail.

Q.5 Rank the level of engagement of the organization with the customer through social media?

Customer engagement is the engagement of the customer with the company. The above graph shows that 128 customers out of 153 are satisfied with the customer engagement at JW Marriott Chandigarh.

Q.6 Rank the following statements to determine why you follow JW Marriott Chandigarh on social media?

Feel Important

Feel accepted

Perceive & Receive Respect

My Self-esteem Increases

They believe that the information received from the social media is truly worth

Good quality of information

Social media is easy to use

Social media provides speedy access to information

JW Marriott Chandigarh on social media site provides good quality of information. People look forward to good and interesting things on social networking sites. As JW Marriott Chandigarh cover all the aspects by providing contest information, Spreads awareness, recipes information etc.

Q.7 Rank the reasons according to your preference that attracts you towards JW Marriott Chandigarh social media?

Spread Awareness

Interactive/Contest/Ideas

Sales/ Discount/coupons

Keep information about service

You like their service

Awareness about the current customers

According to the above charts people follow JW Marriott on social media because they like their service and get to know about various sale/discount currently going on.

Q. 8 Rate the customer experience management (response) of JW Marriott Chandigarh on the basis of performance?

Effective response

Full Transparency

Customer Driven

Information

Fast

People follow JW Marriott Chandigarh on social media sites because they believe that their queries are taken care. They understand the importance of time all the queries are met very fast and don't make the customer wait.

Q 9. Do social media of JW Marriott Chandigarh influence your purchase of its service?

From the above graph out of 153 people 106 believe that their purchase of a service are influenced by what they see on social media.

Q 10: Do the customer controls the environment of the brand through social media?

According to graphical representation 77 people out of 153 believe that most of the time consumer controls the environment as one bad or negative comment on a social networking site can have a negative effect on the company.

CONCLUSION

Social media grown by leap and bounds it is not only influence the classes but also the masses. Use of social media has become very important for all the organization's these days, be it small or a big organization. It helps to reach out and connect with their customer directly. Social media has helped in bridging the gap between people and the organization. Social media increases interactions that help to share, create and exchange information and ideas among each other. Social media is fast and direct way to reach out to the consumers. Customers prefer social media over traditional media. The consumer rely on social media as they believe all their queries are met on time are not kept waiting. They get to know about various services that influence their purchase of the service. The organization should use social media to its maximum to influence people. As in this day and age everyone is fully dependent on internet. Social media helps the company to reach out to people who are far and near a split second. Thus the ideas are reached out faster to more number of people.

LIMITATION

It only caters to those people /consumer who have access to internet. Whereas there is a large population in India who do not have easy access to the internet and many people are not literate. For few people internet is a costly and cannot afford it.

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